

HOME VISITATION AND ITS EFFECT ON THE LEARNING OUTCOMES OF STUDENTS AT RISK OF DROPPING OUT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN DISTRICT II-F, DIVISION OF ANTIPOLO CITY

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Home Visitation and its Effect on the Learning Outcomes of Students at Risk of Dropping Out in Public Secondary Schools in District II-F, Division of Antipolo City

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students-at-risk of dropping out in public secondary schools in District II-F, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2017-2018. The research instrument measured the extent of effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students-at-risk of dropping out as perceived by the teacher-respondents with respect to class participation, task accomplishment and study habits. The study revealed that public elementary school teachers in the District II-F, Division of Antipolo City is female dominated. Most of them have ages 31 years old and above and have been teaching for more than 5 years. Majority of them have not finished graduate education courses. Home visitation have much effect on the learning outcomes of students at risk of dropping out with respect to classroom participation, task accomplishment and study habits. Age and length of service are significant on the teachers' perception on the extent of effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students at risk of dropping out while sex and educational attainment are not significant. It was concluded that teachers have different views regarding the effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students at risk of dropping out when they are grouped according to their age and length of service. On the contrary, sex and educational attainment have nothing to do with their perceptions.

Keywords: *home visitation, learning outcomes, drop-out*

Introduction

Education in its general sense recognizes students' varying needs. It purports and holds the belief that each person prefers different classroom engagement and needs in order to learn. It is an indispensable ingredient of development and a fundamental right of every individual. It plays a vital role in human development and improvement of the individual and the society as a whole. It has been recognized as a central factor of change and progress. Moreover, education is constitutionally a state responsibility with the national government providing some general and special purpose grants. It is the most important vehicle in achieving the goals of every human being and a powerful tool in the development and progress of every individual in particular and of a nation in general.

For this purpose, the schools shall create a functional basic education system that will develop productive and responsible citizens equipped with the essential competencies, skills and values for both life-long learning and employment. Further, the provision clearly expressed that hand-in-hand with different programs are methods and learning styles appropriate to the pupils should be provided in the classroom with utmost guidance to them. However, despite varied programs available for children, dropping out from class is still the number one problem among public schools. Each year, more than a million kids will leave school without earning a high school diploma-that's approximately 7,000 students every day of the academic year. Without that diploma, they'll be more likely to head down a path that leads to lower-paying jobs, poorer health, and the possible continuation of a cycle of poverty that creates immense challenges for families, neighborhoods, and communities.

Beginning a home visit program and bridging the home-school gap does take an amount of planning, training, and funding to be effective. Initially, teachers often voice concerns about the safety of traveling to strange homes, what they should do during a 30-90-minute session, and how to draw appropriate boundaries during the visits. Many other teachers who had never conducted a home visit had concerns about language barriers, parental reactions to visits, and fitting visits into their full schedules. However, after training for the visits and participating in the home visit programs, the majority of teachers found home school visits an effective and innovative tool.

For some students, dropping out is the culmination of years of academic hurdles, missteps, and wrong turns. For others, the decision to drop out is a response to conflicting life pressures the need to help support their family financially or the demands of caring for siblings or their own child. Dropping out is sometimes about students being bored and seeing no connection between academic life and real life. It is about young people feeling disconnected from their peers and from teachers and other adults at school.

Although the reasons for dropping out vary, the consequences of the decision are remarkably similar. Over a lifetime, dropouts typically earn less, suffer from poorer health as adults, and are more likely to wind up in jail than their diploma-earning peers.

At present, basic education students are taught with various learning packages in accordance with the needed competencies required for them. Various approaches are applied in teaching the different subjects so that students would achieve competence in content subjects. However, differences in learning styles hamper the development and growth of the students. More often than not, they are developed compartmentally, mastering the skills they already know and disregarding higher order thinking skills because it does not fit with his/her way of learning. In addition, it has been observed that students do not achieve fluency during the time of instruction

perhaps due to learning environment.

In public secondary schools in the Division of Antipolo City, many students are considered students at risk of dropping out due to tardiness, absenteeism and poor study habits. With these situations, many teachers conduct home visitation to remedy the problems. Hence, the researcher was inspired to conduct this study to find out the impact of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students at risk of dropping out.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students-at-risk of dropping out in public secondary schools in District II-F, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2017-2018. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. educational attainment; and
 - 1.4. length of service?
2. What is the extent of effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students-at-risk of dropping out as perceived by the teacher-respondents with respect to:
 - 2.1. class participation;
 - 2.2. task accomplishment; and
 - 2.3. study habits?
3. Is there a significant difference on the extent of effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students-at-risk of dropping out as perceived by the teacher-respondents with respect to the cited aspects in terms of their profile?

Literature Review

Home visits can establish positive contact and communication with families. They are not a replacement for parent-teacher conferences, but are a process through which teachers demonstrate their support for students' families by visiting the home environment or an alternative location where the family feels at home and comfortable. Home visits should originate from a sincere desire to assist and work with families. Home visits promote proactive interactions through which teachers provide authentic support while recognizing families' strengths.

According to Smith (2010) the use of home visitors to deliver services designed to improve the well-being of children and their families has drawn the increasing interest of policymakers, including President Barack Obama, who last year proposed a federal investment of more than \$8 billion over the next 10 years in programs that use home visitation as a method of service delivery.

Home visitation for Curry (2010) is a method of service delivery used to reach at-risk children and families with a wide range of supports. In the United States, it is estimated that home-visiting programs serve between 400,000 and 500,000 children, about 5 percent of the estimated 10.2 million American children under the age of 6 years who are living in low-income families.

Likewise, Masa (2016) stated that the home-visiting program in the country especially in public schools was found to reduce child maltreatment based on an evaluation. That study reported a 48 percent decline in rates of child abuse and neglect at the time of the 15-year follow up among low-income families who had participated in the program.

Meanwhile, Olivarez (2010) investigated ways by which schools succeed at getting parents involved and examined the levels of home-school communication. This study has investigated schools, parents, and school organizations (such as PTA, school councils, etc) on different ways to get parents involved. In summary, over ninety-percent of the participant principals either agreed or strongly-agreed on the following: Parents are welcomed into their schools, Student-parent handbooks are given out at the beginning of the school year; Information about school events is distributed regularly; and Parents are invited to attend at least one school activity during the school year.

Moreover, a study conducted by Leonardo (2015) on parent involvement revealed that in a child's education is consistently found to be positively associated with a child's academic performance. Results indicated a statistically significant association between parent involvement and a child's academic performance, over and above the impact of the child's intelligence. A multiple mediation model indicated that the child's perception of cognitive competence fully mediated the relation between parent involvement and the child's performance on a standardized achievement test.

Methodology

Research Design

The study applied the descriptive survey research design utilizing a questionnaire-checklist as a tool in gathering the needed data. Zulueta (2010) defines the descriptive survey research design as a process which deals with the relationships between variables, the

testing of the hypothesis and the development of generalizations, principles of theories that have universal validity. It describes and interprets that is. It concerns with conditions or relationships that exist, opinions that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are evident, or trends that are developing. It is primarily concerned with the present although it often considers past events and influences as they relate to condition.

The descriptive survey research design was used to determine the extent of effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of student at risk of dropping out.

Respondents

One hundred percent of the total population of teachers in three public secondary schools in District II-F, Division of Antipolo City were considered as respondents of the study. This consists of 60 teachers. They were described in terms of age, sex, educational attainment and length of service.

Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist as the primary instrument in order to gather the necessary data or information.

The questionnaire has two parts. Part I is about the personal data of the respondents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment and length of service. Part II refers to the extent of effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of student at risk of dropping out with respect to classroom participation, task accomplishment and study habits. Each aspect consists of ten (10) items.

Procedure

The study followed the Gantt Chart of Activities in the conduct of the study. This includes the formulation of the research problem up to the revision of the manuscript and submission of the final copy. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent. After the validation of the instrument, the questionnaire-checklist was administered to the respondents. After the retrieval, the data were encoded and processed. Collected data were presented, interpreted, and analyzed. The researcher then completed the paper and provided conclusion.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of the Selected Variables*

<i>Age</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
51-60 years old	2	3
41-50 years old	4	7
31-40 years old	32	53
21-30 years old	22	37
Total	60	100
Sex		
Male	20	33
Female	40	67
Total	60	100
Educational Attainment		
Masters' Degree	10	17
With MA units	15	25
Bachelor's Degree	35	58
Total	60	100
Length of Service		
20-24 years	4	7
15-19 years	3	5
10-14 years	10	17
5-9 years	31	51
4 years and below	12	20
Total	60	100

As shown in the table, out of 60 teachers 32 or 53 percent have ages 31-40 years old, 22 or 37 percent have ages 21-30 years old and the remaining percentage have ages 41 years old and above. In terms of sex, there are more females than males with 40 or 67 percent female teachers. With regard to their educational attainment, 15 or 35 percent have earned units in Master's degree, 10 or 17 percent have finished their Master's degree and the rest have not pursued their graduate education. As to their length of service, 31 or 51 percent

have been in the service for 5-9 years, 12 or 22 percent have been teaching for 4 years and below and the remaining percentage have been in the service for 10 years and above.

Extent of Effects of Home Visitation on the Learning Outcomes of Students at Risk of Dropping Out as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Table 2. *Extent of Effects of Home Visitation on the Learning Outcomes of Students at Risk of Dropping Out as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents with Respect to Classroom Participation*

<i>Classroom Participation</i>		WX	VI	R
<i>Homeroom visitation encourages student at risk of dropping out to ...</i>				
1.	focus attentively to teachers' explanation of the lesson.	3.48	Moderate	6
2.	enhance interest in attending classes.	3.49	Moderate	5
3.	participate actively in class discussion.	3.21	Moderate	10
4.	show love for learning by asking questions to the teacher.	3.25	Moderate	9
5.	analyze situations both in oral or written activities.	3.57	Much	3
6.	examine a problem thoroughly following the lesson.	3.42	Moderate	8
7.	contribute to brainstorming by sharing experiences.	4.00	Much	2
8.	attend classes regularly.	4.06	Much	1
9.	gain confidence in answering questions.	3.47	Moderate	7
10.	cooperate with classmates in group activities.	3.54	Much	4
Overall WX		3.55	Much	

It can be seen from the table that in terms of classroom participation, the obtained overall weighted was 3.55 and verbally interpreted as Much. In addition, item 8 "attend classes regularly" gained the highest mean of 4.06 interpreted as Much, while item 3 "participate actively in class discussion" has the lowest mean of 3.21 and interpreted as Moderated.

Findings reveal that home visitation conducted by teachers help students at risk to attend classes and participate in classroom activities. This implies that teachers' concern for students through home visitation have positive effects on students' participation in the class. This relates to the ideas of Garcia (2016), that classroom participation can result in insightful comments and interesting connections being made by students, and can foster a high level of energy and enthusiasm in the classroom learning environment. However, poorly managed participation can also lead to instructor frustration and student confusion. Participation is often equated with discussion, which typically involves a lengthy conversation with the whole class.

Table 3. *Extent of Effects of Home Visitation on the Learning Outcomes of Students at Risk of Dropping Out as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents with Respect to Task Accomplishment*

<i>Task Accomplishment</i>		WX	VI	R
<i>Homeroom visitation helps student at risk of dropping out in...</i>				
1.	accomplishing assigned tasks willingly.	4.52	Very Much	1
2.	performing other tasks as instructed by the teacher.	3.98	Much	5
3.	working on assignment regularly.	3.94	Much	6
4.	doing assigned practice exercises.	4.26	Much	2
5.	following the prescribed format in submitting projects.	3.78	Much	7
6.	looking for patterns for school projects.	2.36	Less	10
7.	doing quality projects.	3.65	Much	8
8.	enhancing patience and perseverance in doing school projects.	3.99	Much	4
9.	exerting extra efforts in doing school projects.	4.22	Much	3
10.	taking quizzes and examinations on the scheduled time.	3.54	Much	9
Overall WX		3.82	Much	

As to the effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students at risk of dropping out as perceived by the teacher-respondents with respect to task accomplishment, the overall weighted mean obtained is 3.82 interpreted Much. Among the items, first in rank is "Homeroom visitation helps student at risk of dropping out in accomplishing assigned tasks" with a weighted mean of 4.52 interpreted Very Much. Eight items are interpreted Much while last in rank is the item "Homeroom visitation helps student at risk of dropping out in looking for patterns for school projects" with a weighted mean of 2.36 interpreted Less.

Results reveal that home visitation to students at risk of dropping out has contributed much on their task accomplishment. This implies that teachers believe that reaching out students in their homes could positively affect their learning outcomes in terms of task accomplishment. This is in connection with the statements of Leviste (2009) that one possible cause of slow task initiation is that a child does not have the skills, understanding or knowledge necessary to do the task and is avoiding getting started. It is essential to establish beforehand that the child has the skills, support, and resources necessary to accomplish a task before implementing a plan with the expectation that the task is initiated and completed in a timely manner.

As reflected on the table 3, with respect to study habits, the overall weighted mean obtained is 3.54 interpreted Much. Out of ten items, five items are interpreted Much with first in rank is "Homeroom visitation motivates student at risk of dropping out to enjoy learning

different subjects” with a weighted mean of 4.00. Five items are interpreted Moderate with last in rank is the item “Homeroom visitation motivates student at risk of dropping out feel comfortable in studying everyday lessons” with a weighted mean of 3.22.

Table 4. *Extent of Effects of Home Visitation on the Learning Outcomes of Students at Risk of Dropping Out as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents with Respect to Study Habits*

<i>Study Habits</i>	<i>WX</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
<i>Homeroom visitation motivates student at risk of dropping out to ...</i>			
1. develop good study habits.	3.37	Moderate	7
2. enhance interest in learning different subjects.	3.60	Much	4
3. work on assigned enhancement activities.	3.54	Much	5
4. study the lessons regularly.	3.31	Moderate	8
5. increase patience in doing assigned school work.	3.42	Moderate	6
6. answer questions with confidence.	3.82	Much	2
7. enjoy learning different subjects.	4.00	Much	1
8. increase enthusiasm to study different concepts.	3.28	Moderate	9
9. feel comfortable in studying everyday lessons.	3.22	Moderate	10
10. read notes at home.	3..80	Much	3
Overall WX	3.54	Much	

The results reveal that home visitation has contributed much on the improvement of study habits of students. This implies through home visitation conducted by teachers; students have realized the importance of having good study habits. This relates to the statements of Reyes (2014), that while studying is the best way to grow and attain achievements as a student, it is still, admittedly, a challenging thing to do. There are many distractions around nowadays, such as the Internet, the television, cellphones, and even one’s friends. It is so easy for studying to be sidetracked, as it is often seen as a tedious task, something that takes more effort than is necessary as compared to simply passing and exam or a course.

The Significant Difference on the Extent of Effects of Home Visitation on the Learning Outcomes of Students at Risk of Dropping Out as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents with Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of Their Profile

Table 5. *Computed F-values on the Extent of Effects of Home Visitation on the Learning Outcomes of Students at Risk of Dropping Out as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents with Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of Their Profile*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Fcomp</i>	<i>p-values</i>	<i>Ho</i>	<i>VI</i>
Classroom Participation	4.55	.009	Rejected	Significant
Task Accomplishment	4.37	.034	Rejected	Significant
Study Habits	3.97	.028	Rejected	Significant
<i>Sex</i>				
Classroom Participation	1.07	.854	Accepted	Not Significant
Task Accomplishment	1.22	.776	Accepted	Not Significant
Study Habits	1.28	.882	Accepted	Not Significant
<i>Educational Attainment</i>				
Classroom Participation	1.44	.095	Accepted	Not Significant
Task Accomplishment	1.25	.299	Accepted	Not Significant
Study Habits	1.94	.075	Accepted	Not Significant
<i>Length of Service</i>				
Classroom Participation	4.95	.004	Rejected	Significant
Task Accomplishment	3.88	.014	Rejected	Significant
Study Habits	4.96	.038	Rejected	Significant

The table reveals that in terms of age and length of service, with respect to all aspects, the computed F-values obtained probability values less than .05. This rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents on the extent of effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students at risk of dropping out with respect to the different aspects in terms of age and length of service. On the other hand, in terms of sex and educational attainment, the null hypothesis is accepted since the obtained probability values are all less than .05.

It could be deduced from the results that age and length of service are significant on the teachers’ perception. This implies that teachers who are more matured and experienced may have different views regarding home visitation. This also implies that regardless of sex and educational attainment, teachers believe that home visitation has significant effects on the learning outcomes of student at risk of dropping out. This is in relation with the statements of Wales (2014), that home visits can give teachers the insight they need to help all students succeed. Establishing a positive relationship with students' families-is an important tool in school reform, particularly in low-income, urban districts where educators traditionally struggle to build parent involvement. Starting the year off with teacher visits to students' homes, with such visits serving as invitations to parents to become partners in their children's education, is, in fact, one of the easiest ways to establish relationships.

Conclusions

The study concluded that teachers have different views regarding the effects of home visitation on the learning outcomes of students at risk of dropping out when they are grouped according to their age and length of service. On the contrary, sex and educational attainment have nothing to do with their perceptions.

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